

Pesticides Influence on the Honey Bee Colony

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Abstract:

Honey bees are well known for the crucial role they play in biodiversity by producing high-quality food, thus assisting in the establishment of a worldwide food supply. Unfortunately, a group of chemicals that are harmful by nature regularly endanger bee populations as they are sprayed in fields for crop protection. Pesticides are poisonous compounds used on agricultural areas to get rid of unwanted pests. As a result, pesticides have a lot of negative impacts on the honey bee colony. In this paper, we'll go over each of the different ways that bees might come into contact with pesticides. Additionally, the level of toxicity that these pesticides possess can be taken into account because a higher dose equates to a higher level of mortality. When these insecticides used to protect crops are exposed through various paths, there are multiple problems that have sublethal effects on honey bees. Numerous behavioural and physiological changes, including aberrant movement, memory loss, and changes in the development of the larvae and the queen, occur in bees. In this review paper, we will see in detail the effects caused by pesticides in the honey bee colony.

Keywords: pesticides, sublethal effects, *Apis mellifera*, developmental problems

Introduction:

Apis mellifera, or honey bees, are important socio-economic insects (Kapahi, 2022) that have historically contributed to the development of agriculture by providing crucial services for food production and pollination. Honey, a sweet and viscous liquid made by honeybees from floral nectar, has a high mineral content as well as vitamins, enzymes, and other nutrients. It is acknowledged as a more nutrient-dense alternative to sugar and in terms of carbohydrates (Sharma. S et al, 2021) primarily contains fructose (about 38.5%) and glucose (31.0%). It is used as food or medicines globally and due to its significance, honey is used extensively both for nutritional and medical purposes, including the treatment of tumors, wounds, eye issues, ulcers, measles, cough, and sore throat. Due to its many health benefits, even infants who consume honey grow more quickly, have less anxiety, and perform better when they get older (Ajibola et al, 2012). In addition to producing honey, honey bees also produce a variety of products that are extremely beneficial to humans, including royal jelly, pollen, propolis, and beeswax. Considering the importance of honey bees to the agri-food sector, it is currently unclear how their populations manage stress brought on by nature and agriculture, or to what degree this stress accounts for recent increases in recorded fatalities.

Since ancient times, beekeepers are aware that honey bees benefit from flowers from trees, shrubs, and even agricultural crops as it helped in the growth of the colonies. Some of the minor

issues they occasionally had to deal with included unpredictable weather that could lower flower production during especially bad years and the sporadic infection by diseases, parasites, and microbial infections that could wipe out entire colonies of bees (van Engelsdorp et al, 2010). However in the recent years they had to battle with a new problem called pesticides that are sprayed over the crops, forests for controlling insect pests .Pesticides are chemical substances that are used to prevent or eliminate pests that damage crops and lower farm output. With the rising demand of food in a developing country like India, agriculture may achieve tremendous productivity gains by applying adequate amount of pesticides. However, when these pesticides are used excessively or inappropriately, the slow breakdown of pesticides can result in environmental contamination of the water, land, air, agricultural produce, and, tangentially, people (Hamilton & Crossley, 2004). Low exposure levels of pesticides do not appear to have any long-term adverse effects on adult humans. However, high concentrations of these compounds' toxicity are undeniably dangerous to mammals, including people, birds, and humans. Pesticides may be taken into the body and accumulate in the fat, liver, kidneys, and salivary glands, increasing the chance of developing a number of ailments .In accordance with other epidemiological research, high levels of pesticide exposure are linked to a higher chance of developing chronic illnesses, such as cancer, cardiotoxicity, Parkinson's disease, diabetes mellitus, neurological impairments, birth defects, and reproductive problems.

Monitoring pesticide levels in honey provides information on pesticides used in agricultural crops near beehives, which aids in determining the possible risk this product has to consumer health. In many nations, the legal maximum permissible amount of residual pesticides in honey (MRLs) has been set by law. The MRLs for amitraz, bromopropylate, coumaphos, cyamizole, flumetrine, and fluvalinate have been developed in Germany, Italy, and Switzerland. In Germany, these MRLs range from 0.01 to 0.1 mg/kg, in Switzerland, they range from 5 to 500 mg/kg, and in Italy, they are 10 mg/kg. (Bogdanov, 1999) Although many national authorities have established pesticide residue thresholds (MRLs) for honey, the lack of uniformity hinders international marketing and commerce. In spite of these regulations, the number of managed honey bee (*Apis mellifera* L.) colonies in the United States decreased from 6 million in 1947, the first year DDT was used in agriculture, to less than 3 million in 2010 (Ellis J et al, 2012).

Routes of exposure:

Bees can be exposed to environmental chemicals through ingestion, contact, or, to a lesser amount, from breathing involatile airborne particles.

The majority of insecticides and pesticides that are applied to crops afterward may disperse from the site of application and be carried by winds to nearby regions that are travelling near the treated crop. Bees that settle or travel on contaminated surfaces like soil, grass, owers foliage, etc. end up consuming contaminated pollen and nectar or being exposed directly (Kopit & Pitts-Singer et al, 2018). It is extremely lethal as the spray solutions include concentrated quantities of chemicals that can kill a bee with a single droplet of insecticide

An additional group of herbicides known as systemic insecticides is frequently used to coat seeds in crops. Pneumatic drilling planters are used to plant the treated seeds into the earth, and as a result, heavily insecticide-contaminated dust is generated as a result of friction between the treated seeds and the machinery. Pesticides are further consumed by agricultural plants, and it is discovered that as they grow, they persist in all of the plant's components, including nectar and pollen from blossoms. The visiting forager bees which collect the contaminated pollen and nectar is affected. Moreover, during early morning guttation, these pesticides are present in

highly concentrated droplets that are formed. All of these have potential to harm bees when they are brought in contact with them. (Botias C et al, 2017)

Water exposure is yet another source of exposure. Bees also consume water to regulate their body temperature. Workers of honey bees consume and gather water from neighbouring ponds, moisten vegetation, and prepare larval brood. Several pesticides contaminate streams, creeks, and ponds in agricultural areas by releasing residues from plants after rain, dispersion from spray applications, or runoff from polluted ground surfaces that eventually move into the water and appear there (Belden J B et al, 2007).

Direct contact with contaminated nesting materials can expose solitary bees, including adult females and developing stages, to fungicide. Inadvertent consumption of polluted soil, leaf debris, or water while manipulating these materials for nest construction or when cleaning body parts might also expose female solitary bees to residues orally. Moreover, if pesticide residues seep into food supplies from the soil or leaves, larval exposure via nesting materials may happen orally (Kopit & Pitts-Singer et al, 2018). Adult male solitary bees are most likely to come into contact with pesticide residues when they are foraging, sleeping on plants, or inside hives. Fungicides used on seedlings can remain in soil for years and in tiny amounts in plant tissues for a number of months.

Toxicology:

Pesticides are toxic compounds that are used to eliminate undesired organisms interrupting specific metabolic pathways, neural activity, and occasionally even the development of the organisms being controlled. The toxicity of pesticides, particularly insecticides used in agriculture, may have negative impacts and lead to undesirable outcomes, even to the degree where bee colonies are exterminated.

The levels of toxicity of various insecticides vary, as Contact insecticides are typically sprayed on plants, where they can harm bees as they travel to nearby surfaces. Contrarily, systemic insecticides are typically added to the soil or applied to seeds before moving up into the plant's parts. Different species with similar metabolisms are also impacted by every kind of pesticide, although often to a lower degree, as it is not just the target group of animals that are toxic. A helpful statistic for figuring out the lethality of a specific pesticide and figuring out sublethal exposure in adult honey bees is the dose at which 50% of the population perishes (LD50)

Since estimates of LD50 may vary by time of contamination and method of administration, understanding the particular oral and dermal LD50 of different pesticides can be a helpful indicator of pesticide-associated risk

Although doses less than the LD50 are regarded as "sublethal," they can nonetheless result in mortality in 20 to 30 percent of the population, depending on the species. Sublethal levels typically result in toxic consequences that impair an organism's ability to operate normally and maintain their health without actually killing it.

The immediate toxic effect of pesticides on bees, which can happen through touch or intake, is commonly measured by the LD50. When used with variable LD50 values, the Hazard Quotient ($HQ = \text{application rate}/LD50$) can be an effective method for estimating the risk of applying pesticides in the field. Bees exposed to acute pesticides may exhibit a variety of symptoms, such as agitation, vomiting, wing paralysis, an abdomen arch resembling the sting reflex, and uncoordinated movement. Depending on how the substance is consumed, acute toxicity may change whereas neonicotinoids are more poisonous when consumed orally, also many pesticides can be dangerous when administered topically.

Pesticides impair behaviour, cognition, and motor skills:

Insecticides and biological targets can interact molecularly, which could have an adverse effect on behavior, motor abilities, and cognition. Honey bees are an example of an organism that uses individual cognition to explore environment, adjust to new surroundings and meet the hive requirements. Insect vision and reasoning are best modeled after honey bees. Bees have shown they can pick up new ideas and rules quickly and use them to solve problems. The aggregate brain systems known as cognition are involved in mental processing, attentiveness, thinking, knowledge, analysis, and resolving issues. Early investigations on the effects of pesticides on memory focused on the responses of bees trained to visit a feeding site to the effects of the organophosphate ethyl- parathion on time memory (Schricker et al, 1974). At a sublethal dosage, parathion altered the honey bees' circadian rhythm, causing a change in visiting hours to the morning. A common approach to gauge olfactory learning, which enables honey bees to learn to associate a fragrance with compensation, is the proboscis extension reflex (PER). In view of this fact, honey bees treated with imidacloprid, a class of neonicotinoid family causes a decline in learning performance under both acute and subchronic exposure, which is explored by looking at the conditioned PER. It may also reduce brain's propensity to associate the predator with fear (Decourtye et al, 2004). Infact, Fipronil also yields the same result based on leased on learning although it gives different effects as when given to the thorax, a modest dose inhibits old-factory memory, whereas a high dose modifies side-specific antennal tactile learning. Pesticides also have an impact on orientation and navigation in terms of cognition. During the waggle communication dance, parathion stops bees from informing other bees where food sources are located by causing them to change to an incorrect angle (Stephen and Schricker et al, 1970). Pesticides such as dialmethrin also disrupt return flights by interfering with homing behavior and increasing phototropism in foragers, while it is unclear if they affect other bodily processes including vision and orientation.

The inability of honey bees to effectively control their metabolic pathways in response to environmental changes can lead to behavioral changes in the species, which illustrates the bees' physiological effects. The primary factor in the bees' altered behavior is foraging. In general, pesticides change the way that foragers behave because they interfere with brain function, making it impossible for them to fulfill the neural programs that control their behavior. They also change the way that feeding occurs, which affects the colony and results in nutritional deficiencies. When bees are exposed to fenitrothion, an organophosphate, the number of foraging insects dramatically decreases. Conversely, for bees treated with parathion, the results are more complicated (Guez et al, 2005). Bees treated with higher doses of parathion visited the feed more frequently, but bees treated with lower doses experienced a dual effect that included a decrease in foraging activity and an increase in evidence supporting the existence of molecular targets with varying affinities for methyl-parathion. Moreover, heightened attraction to the food, energetic stress, or increased foraging activity as a result of a brief hyperactivation of the cholinergic transmission could account for an increase in visit frequency brought on by methyl-parathion. The honey bees' motor abilities are also compromised by pesticide. Neonicotinoid exposure typically results in increased grooming time and an impairing of the righting reflex, which in turn leads to greater time spent upside down. Exposure to nicotine and thiamethoxam often increased grooming behavior

Pesticides affect honey bee immunity:

Mass colony losses have been attributed to biotic and abiotic environmental stresses, with pesticides being one of the most horrifying causes. Pesticide exposure sets off immunological reactions and stress pathways that ultimately impact the survival of honey bee colonies. . There also exists an intricate and detrimental interplay between pesticides and pathogens .Honey bees that have been exposed to pesticides have greater rates of fungal, and viral disease. Honey bee health may be impacted by infectious agents and parasites, increasing infestations and infections in colonies with weakened immune systems brought on by inadequate nutrition and chemical exposure, respectively (Di Prisco G et al,2013)

Bee colonies have been seen to have a lower level of immunological competence due to the increased impact of infections caused by pesticides such as neonicotinoids. Neonicotinoids such as clothianidin increase the expression of a Leucine Rich Repeat (LRR) protein, a negative modulator of NF- κ B activation in insects. This protein is probably involved in the physiological down-regulation of the immunological response, as described in other animal species (Ting & Davis et al, 2005). An agonist of the acetylcholine receptor can have such an effect that it implies the existence of neural reflex circuits in insects that control the immune response. This is similar to what has been observed in vertebrates, where acetylcholine receptor binding inhibits NF- κ B activation in immune cells, thereby downregulating the immune response. Neonicotinoids, which may be produced by bees, disrupt this regulatory mechanism, which in turn causes the down-regulation of antiviral barriers under NF- κ B control immunological response, which in turn promotes the proliferation of DWV (Di Prisco G et al, 2013). Hence it lead to the increase in the defective wing virus infection titers.

Insect immunity is greatly impacted by the interactions between insecticides and infections. Insect immunity is impacted by pesticides, specifically organophosphates and organochlorines, in terms of haemocyte count, differentiation, and phagocytosis. It effects the cellular immunity of the insects. Immune defence is known to boost granulocyte and haemoglobin counts. An insect subjected to an organophosphate has an increase in total hemocyte count, prohemocyte and plasmatocyte counts decrease, and granulocyte counts rise. Organochlorines result in a decrease in the overall number of hemocytes, with prohemocytes and plasmatocytes increasing and granulocytes decreasing (George et al, 2004). It has not been investigated how these cellular alterations impacted this insect's immunity in general or its immunological response in particular. Dieldrin, a cyclodiene, and endosulfan, an organochlorine, are pesticides that have been found to have an impact on encapsulation.

Moreover, honey bees engage in a number of hygienic behavior's that lessen the number of pathogens in their colonies, most notably self- or mutual grooming and the getting rid of dead bees. When pesticides like imidacloprid interfere with this natural mechanism, worker bees exposed to them show less sanitary removal of freeze-killed brood, which disturbs the entire process (Boucias et al, 1996). Moreover pesticides like coumaphos, amitraz and tau fluvalinate made workers to groom less which increased the burden on varroa destructors.

Pesticides negatively affect reproduction and development:

Honey bee queen longevity is primarily determined by normal development to sexual maturity and suitable changes in behavior, anatomy, and physiology that follow successful mating.

Consequently, adverse impacts on vulnerable queen reproductive systems that lead to anomalous physiology or anatomy, or that hinder spermatozoa storage or oviposition, may necessitate an expensive replacement of the queen by the colony. Honey bees when exposed to field realistic doses of neonicotinoid insecticides at field-realistic doses while developing, suffer from serious consequences. It results in increased ovarian size which influences the development of the queen's reproductive systems. Pesticides like imidacloprid and coumaphos also cause a decline in the viability of the sperm that is stored in the queen's spermatheca. And at high concentrations, neonicotinoid pesticides, which function as neonicotinic receptors in the nervous system, may be the legitimate cause because they cause neuronal hyperexcitation, which disrupts the physiology and anatomy of the queen, which is in charge of transporting and storing freshly received spermatozoa during mating. Pesticides have an impact on drones as well. Lowered sperm transfer and fertilisation may restrict the development of a genetically varied workforce, jeopardising the ability to divide labour and respond to disease. Neonicotinoids and phenylpyrazoles, which are present in sublethal amounts, decrease sperm viability and prevent the fertilisation of queens and the formation of diploid workers (Sherman et al, 1988)

Although pesticides have a reputation for interfering with reproduction, the exposure of honey bees to pesticides during their larval stage results in various negative effects that can be sublethal. Pesticide exposure has an impact on the developing larvae's survival, morphology, and maturation. Honey bee larvae when exposed to miticide class pesticide such as amitraz, coumaphos and fluvalinate, the chances of honey bees surviving to adulthood are considerably decreased. Additionally, they display malformed antennae and hypopharyngeal glands. Due to their production of components of brood food, hypopharyngeal glands are vital for the feeding and development of larvae (Heylen et al, 2011). Additionally, the hypopharyngeal gland shrank in size, which may have an impact on the health of the colony. It also results in deformed antennae, including shorter flagella and scapes and even leads to delayed maturation.

Author's Contribution

Merina contributed in the writing and editing of the review article. Dr. Lovleen designed, written, reviewed, edited and conceptualised the work.

Declaration

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interests.

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